

NEED AND SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP PROJECTS.

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Abstract. *This article provides a significant analysis of the need and specific features of public-private partnership projects and the implementation of the public-private partnership mechanism .*

Keywords: *public-private partnership, complex, systematic, concept, didactic and concession.*

НЕОБХОДИМОСТЬ И ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПРОЕКТОВ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННО-ЧАСТНОГО ПАРТНЕРСТВА.

Аннотация. *В статье представлен содержательный анализ необходимости и особенностей проектов государственно-частного партнерства и реализации механизма государственно-частного партнерства.*

Ключевые слова: *государственно-частное партнерство, комплексное, системное, концепция, дидактика и концессия.*

An important aspect of the implementation of the mechanism of public-private partnership is planning the expenses of preschool educational institutions and taking measures to increase the transparency of their spending, increasing the openness and independence of their activities , which serves as a basis for establishing public-private partnership and increases their investment attractiveness.

The introduction of PPP into the preschool education system is still relevant and the fastest effective method today. The resources, experience, incentive system and other advantages of the private sector provide opportunities for rapid development and modernization of the preschool education system without requiring large expenditures from the state budget. PPP has the ability to address a number of negative trends in the preschool education system, especially deficiencies in management and quality assurance. At the moment, the stabilization of the economic situation in Uzbekistan, the growth dynamics of economic sectors, the deepening of democratic principles in political life create very favorable conditions for the development of mutually beneficial cooperation of the private sector.

In the current conditions, the introduction of the public-private partnership mechanism into the preschool education system provides the following opportunities:

to dramatically increase children's coverage of preschool education in a relatively short period of time at the national level;

providing all regions of the country with equal opportunities in the process of preparing children for school;

enrolling a certain number of children from families in need of social assistance and a special contingent to preschool education under preferential conditions;

to set preferential amounts of parents' fees for them (in amounts not exceeding those established for state preschool educational organizations in this location);

priority admission of children from families in need of social assistance to preschool education;

improving the quality of the educational process by introducing modern conditions into the system as a result of creating a healthy competitive environment among preschool educational organizations and striving to attract highly qualified pedagogues;

reduction of expenditures from the republican budget for the establishment of state kindergartens and financing of their activities.

In UIDjumaniyazov's opinion, public-private partnership is successfully used in developed countries and is a necessary and effective mechanism for further development of the business environment, small business and private sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan. It depends on the readiness of the state and business for mutual relations. The international and local experience accumulated in our country over the past 26 years shows that public-private partnership can attract unused reserves and expand resource bases for economic development, increase the efficiency of state and public property management, attract additional new resources to the public sector, budget deficit, etc. it is one of the main mechanisms that allow to reduce the tension of problems, to combine the potential of state management and private principles in economic management, investments, resources, innovations.

Based on the investment program, many state pre-school educational institutions are built every year, and the existing ones are being renovated. However, it is not possible to significantly increase the coverage. The annual increase of the population by more than 800,000 children is an additional burden on coverage.

Broad inclusion of the private sector in the field, faster modernization of the field, development of facilities of preschool educational organizations, provision of socially important services to the population will allow expanding the socio-economic capabilities of the state in terms of implementing the institution of public-private partnership, and will serve to further increase the efficiency of management in social and other fields. does.

The main principles of public-private partnership are as follows ¹:

equality of state and private partners before the law;

transparency of established rules and procedures in the implementation of public-private partnership;

fairness and impartiality in the selection of private partners;

not to allow parties to be discriminated against;

prevent corruption.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public-Private Partnership", approval of the concept of the public-private partnership project, making changes and (or) additions to it:

Approval of the concept of public-private partnership projects with a total project cost of more than one million US dollars and up to ten million US dollars equivalent, changes or additions

¹Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public-Private Partnership" dated May 10, 2019 No. ORQ-537

to it is carried out by the relevant state body (Preschool Education Agency) based on an agreement with the Public-Private Partnership Agency.

The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan independently approves the concept of equivalent public-private partnership projects with a total project cost of more than ten million US dollars, making changes and additions to it.

Since none of the project sums in the public-private partnership contracts signed by the Agency for Preschool Education exceeded one million US dollars, the approval of the contract for all projects was carried out independently by the Agency for Preschool Education (formerly the Ministry of Preschool Education).

According to the law, the term of validity of the agreements based on public-private partnership must not be less than three years and not more than forty-nine years.

Public-private partnership projects were among the first to be introduced in the system of preschool education in our Republic, and today they are in the first place in terms of the number of implemented projects.

The most popular form of public-private partnership projects in the field of preschool education is family-based non-governmental preschool education organizations.

The main difference of family non-governmental pre-school education organizations from other forms is that budget allocations or preferential loans are not provided for the project. After the project starts working, subsidies will be allocated from the Republican budget next month depending on the actual work done. Another feature of family non-governmental preschool education organizations is that agreements are signed for a period of 3 years.

Family non-state pre-school education organizations were initially established based on the Government's decision of July 30, 2018 "On approval of regulations on the procedure for issuing permits for the activities of family non-state pre-school education organizations and family non-state pre-school education organizations". As a result of the extensive incentives allocated to this form of public-private partnership, the demand for signing the deal exceeded expectations. Over the past 5 years, 24,463 public-private partnership agreements have been signed and projects launched. About 2 trillion soms are required from the republican budget to finance these projects.

On August 2, 2022, this decision became invalid and the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to simplify public-private partnership relations in the field of preschool education with the help of modern digital technologies" was adopted.

Based on this decision, applications for signing a public-private partnership agreement for the establishment of family-type non-governmental preschool educational organizations will now be submitted online. Within the limits of the resources determined by the agency, contracts are signed first in neighborhoods with low coverage indicators.

Another distinctive feature of public-private partnership projects in the field of preschool education is that for the first time in history, loans were allocated for the establishment of public-private partnership projects in the field of preschool education for a period of fifteen years with a three-year grace period of one percent.

Another distinctive feature is that if children from low-income families and those in need of social assistance are educated in the amount of not less than 25% of the total number of children

in the non-state preschool education organization, the property will be left at the disposal of the private partner after the expiration of the signed agreements. If 15 percent of the total number of children being educated is to educate children from low-income families or families in need of social assistance and children from families belonging to a special contingent, and if preferential amounts of parents' fees are established for them (in an amount not exceeding the general amount set for state preschool education organizations in this area), the property belongs to the state partner. is left to his discretion.

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